

KEY FEATURES AND DEVELOPMENTS IN ELEMENTARY EDUCATION IN INDIA: PROGRESS AND CHALLENGES

Madan Ghoshal

Research Scholar, Department of Education, Seacom Skills University, Birbhum, West Bengal.

Paper Received On: 21 May 2024

Peer Reviewed On: 25 June 2024

Published On: 01 July 2024

Abstract

Elementary education is critically important as it lays the groundwork for an individual's lifelong learning journey. Numerous initiatives and schemes have been introduced to prioritize the primary education of children from disadvantaged, marginalized, and socio-economically backward communities. This study aims to explore the importance of elementary education in India. In 1950, Article 45 of the Constitution, under the Directive Principles of State Policy, mandated that the State should strive to provide free and compulsory education for all children up to the age of fourteen within ten years of the Constitution's commencement. Since then, several policy documents, including each Five Year Plan, the 1968 National Policy on Education, and the revised 1992 National Policy on Education, have sought to enhance India's efforts towards achieving Universal Elementary Education (UEE).

Keywords: *Primary Education, Educational Infrastructure, Right to Education Act, Institutions, Educators, Pupils, Initiatives, Policies*

1. Introduction

Education is integral to the holistic development of an individual's personality and the socio-economic progress of a nation. Elementary education is considered the cornerstone for the personal growth of individuals and the collective welfare of the country. In India, elementary education is the bedrock of compulsory schooling, essential for individual development. It follows pre-school or nursery education and precedes secondary education. Since India gained independence, both central and state governments have actively worked towards expanding primary formal and non-formal education to achieve Universalization of Elementary Education (UEE). The current challenge lies in enhancing existing educational reforms and promoting

local planning and management strategies to strengthen and improve elementary education (Chapter I – Introduction, n.d.).

UEE remains an elusive goal in many parts of the world. The central and state governments, along with other organizations, are committed to advancing elementary education. The 86th Constitutional Amendment Act of 2002 established education as a fundamental right for children aged six to fourteen years. The Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act of 2009 mandates free education for all children up to fourteen years. Education is recognized as a crucial factor for social and economic progress. UEE has created opportunities for individuals, fostering their social and economic development. Education aims not only to enhance individual knowledge but also to improve the overall quality of life (Chapter I – Introduction, n.d.).

2. Management Structures in Education

Effective management structures are vital in education, encompassing buildings, infrastructure, materials, equipment, technology, resources, and finances. Additionally, the teaching-learning processes, classroom management, curriculum, instructional methods, discipline, and communication are crucial components. Educational institutions aim to provide quality education, fostering student growth and development. Besides education, other critical areas include extracurricular activities, learning materials, technology, facilities, skilled teachers, and efficient management functions such as planning, organizing, controlling, leading, recruiting, and directing.

A comprehensive review of Education For All's management structures must consider the structures, processes, and functioning (Mukhopadhyay, Ramkumar, & Vasavi, 2009). Effective management in education involves admission processes, teacher recruitment, and overall operational tasks. School members need to be skilled, proficient, capable, and professional to implement these structures successfully.

The National Plan of Action highlights the importance of management structures at national and state levels, involving senior officials in monitoring and coordinating educational roles. The District Primary Education Program (DPEP) has increased the number of institutions involved in public education delivery. Areas needing improvement include evaluation procedures for student education, institutional structures, teacher performance, and policy practices. Evaluation helps identify weaknesses and implement necessary improvements. This area emphasizes examining internal structures of state departments and institutions involved in

programs like DPEP and Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) to achieve Education For All (EFA) goals (Mukhopadhyay, Ramkumar, & Vasavi, 2009).

To ensure effective management structures, key functions such as planning, organizing, controlling, leading, recruiting, and directing must be considered. Planning involves developing rules and policies to enhance productivity. Organizing focuses on events, tests, proceedings, and competitions. Controlling maintains discipline and resolves conflicts. Leaders guide teachers and students, while recruitment emphasizes qualifications, experience, and communication skills. Directing involves principals guiding teachers and staff, and teachers guiding students, ensuring discipline and fostering qualities like diligence and resourcefulness.

3. Major Goals of Universalization of Elementary Education (UEE)

UEE has been a crucial educational development goal in India since independence. Article 45 of the Directive Principles of State Policy commits to ensuring free and compulsory education for all, though this was not initially achieved, leading to low school enrollments and participation. Government initiatives like the National Policy of Education, 1986, and the revised Program of Action, 1992, aimed to transform elementary education, focusing on improving access, reducing dropouts, and enhancing learning achievements for children aged six to fourteen years. The 83rd Constitutional Amendment reinforces elementary education as a fundamental right, expected to boost primary school enrollment (Chapter I – Introduction, n.d.).

3.1 Universal Access

Universal access involves enrolling all children, including girls and marginalized groups like Scheduled Castes, Scheduled Tribes, and Other Backward Classes. It ensures primary school availability within one kilometer for all children and aims to improve the primary-to-upper primary school ratio from 1:2 to 1:4, increasing girls' participation at the upper primary stage.

3.2 Universal Retention

Universal retention focuses on reducing drop-out rates at the elementary school level. Creating conducive school environments encourages students to attend and enjoy learning. Improving school facilities and providing necessary materials are crucial for student retention.

3.3 Universal Attainment

Universal attainment ensures all primary level children achieve a minimum level of learning, introducing this concept at the upper primary stage on a large scale. Primary students should

develop basic literacy skills, while upper primary stages should see increased student numbers and improved educational attainment.

3.4 Universal Monitoring

Local level committees, including women and teachers, are essential for overseeing primary education. Enhancing UEE's monitoring system ensures goals and objectives are met effectively.

4. Important Areas of Elementary Education

Key areas in elementary education include the number of schools, teachers, and enrollment categorized by school type and management. School reputation depends on student numbers, teacher qualifications, experience, teaching processes, instructional methods, learning materials, and facilities. Effective management and administration are vital for efficient task implementation and community reputation.

Classrooms are central to learning, and students should feel comfortable to enhance their understanding. Proper facilities, seating arrangements, climate control, and teaching materials are essential. Attractive classrooms with pictures, drawings, and other concepts encourage students to attend and understand lessons, improving curriculum and instructional methods.

Teaching and learning processes are crucial, with elementary concepts being manageable and supported by parents at home. Parents assist with homework, tests, and projects, making elementary education foundational for literacy skills like reading, writing, and arithmetic.

Despite well-organized teaching and learning processes, student evaluation is necessary to assess performance. Evaluations identify weaknesses and formulate improvement measures through tests, exams, projects, and assignments. Evaluation also considers homework quality, decorum, and absenteeism rates.

School physical environments vary in size, classrooms, teachers, students, and surroundings. Learning and development are influenced by these conditions. Elementary students enjoy outdoor activities, and providing facilities like parks and swings enhances their learning experience.

Teachers in elementary schools should be well-trained, experienced, and knowledgeable about teaching materials and strategies. They should be caring and approachable, making young students feel comfortable and supported in the school environment.

Extracurricular activities are vital for student growth, including handicrafts, sports, physical activities, yoga, music, and games. These activities stimulate enthusiasm for learning and are

integral to the educational process. Schools promoting extracurricular participation motivate students and make learning enjoyable.

For elementary education development, periodic analysis is essential to identify areas for improvement. Introducing new materials, facilities, and activities enhances learning. Teachers should communicate with parents to address improvement areas and ensure efficient teaching-learning processes.

5. Features of Elementary Education

The characteristics that have defined elementary education since the country gained independence continue to be relevant today. Key features of elementary education include:

5.1 Enrolment

5.1.1 Increase in Enrolment Rates: Since the 1990s, there has been a significant rise in the enrolment rates for elementary education due to various initiatives, including recruiting local teachers, increasing the number of schools, providing mid-day meals, and offering incentives and scholarships.

5.1.2 Parental and Student Attitudes: Recognition of education's importance has grown, leading to higher enrolment. However, disinterest from parents or students can arise from poorly organized teaching processes, lack of creative activities, inadequate school management, and unsuitable school environments. Enhancements in these areas are essential to boost enrolment rates.

5.2 Equity

5.2.1 Persistent Inequalities: Despite improvements in education, inequalities persist based on regions, genders, castes, classes, ethnicities, religions, and other marginalized groups. For example, while the average literacy rate in India was 65.4% in 2001, it varied significantly from 48% in Bihar to 91% in Kerala.

5.2.2 Drop-out Rates: Higher drop-out rates are observed among deprived, marginalized, and socio-economically backward sections of society. Gender differences are notable among Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes for children aged 6 to 14. Measures to eliminate gender disparities and provide equal opportunities are crucial.

5.3 Quality

5.3.1 Importance of Quality Education: Quality in elementary education is critical and can be improved with a meaningful curriculum, effective instructional methods, appropriate

materials and equipment, technology, conducive physical environments, and adequate resources like libraries.

5.3.2 Teacher's Role: Teachers are pivotal in enhancing school quality, especially in rural areas where they are the main representatives of the education system. Effective teaching-learning methods, availability of materials, and improved communication between teachers and students are essential for quality education.

5.4 Effectiveness

5.4.1 Systemic and Structural Deficiencies: Government schools often face systemic and structural issues. Effectiveness in schools is achieved through proficient management of planning, organizing, leading, directing, recruiting, and controlling.

5.4.2 Teacher Responsibilities: Teachers play a significant role in maintaining school effectiveness. However, issues such as high absenteeism, ineffective teaching methods, and engagement in non-teaching tasks can lead to increased drop-out rates. Promoting equal opportunities, effective teaching methods, and a conducive learning environment are necessary for effectiveness.

6. The Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act, 2009 (RTE Act)

6.1 Legal Framework: The RTE Act, passed in August 2009, ensures the right to free and compulsory education for children aged 6 to 14 years. It mandates free admission, attendance, and completion of elementary education without anxiety or pressure.

6.2 Provisions: The Act prohibits physical punishment, mental harassment, and other barriers to education. It emphasizes curriculum development for holistic child development and ensures the safety and protection of children's rights.

6.3 Implementation: The Act outlines responsibilities for governments, local authorities, and parents. It sets standards for Pupil Teacher Ratios, infrastructure, school working days, and teacher working hours. Proper teacher deployment and the prohibition of non-educational work are also covered.

6.4 Programs and Schemes

6.4.1 Operation Blackboard: Launched in 1987-88, this scheme aims to improve classroom environments by providing infrastructural facilities, additional teachers, and teaching-learning materials to primary and upper primary schools.

6.4.2 Restructuring and Reorganization of Teacher Education: Started in 1987, this scheme strengthens the institutional base of teacher training through various programs and the

establishment of District Institutes of Education and Training (DIETs) and Colleges of Teacher Education (CTEs).

6.4.3 District Primary Education Program (DPEP): Initiated in 1994 with international assistance, DPEP focuses on achieving universal primary education through district-specific planning, teacher training, and infrastructure development.

6.4.3.1 ShikshaKarmi and LokJumbish Projects: These projects in Rajasthan aim to universalize elementary education and improve quality in backward villages with a focus on community participation.

6.4.3.2 MahilaSamakhya: Launched in 1989, this project focuses on the education and empowerment of rural women, particularly those from marginalized groups.

6.4.3.3 Mid-Day Meal Scheme: Initiated in 1995, this program aims to improve enrolment, retention, and nutritional status of primary school students by providing cooked meals.

6.4.3.4 Non-Formal Education (NFE) and EGS & AIE: These schemes address out-of-school children through non-formal education centers, bridge courses, and other alternative education strategies.

6.4.3.5 Janshala (GOI-UN) Programme: A collaborative effort with UN agencies, this program aims to make primary education accessible and effective, especially for girls and marginalized groups.

6.4.3.6 SarvaShikshaAbhiyan: Launched towards the end of the Ninth Plan, this program aims to provide elementary education to all children by 2010 through community-owned quality education initiatives.

7. Conclusion

Elementary education in India must reach deprived, marginalized, and socio-economically backward sections of society. Ensuring equitable access to quality education, improving infrastructure, and addressing inequalities are vital. Increased recognition of education's importance has led to improvements, but continuous efforts are needed to meet the educational needs and requirements of all individuals.

References

- Chapter I - Introduction. (n.d.). Retrieved January 11, 2018, from <http://ssa.nic.in/quality-docs/RTE%20SSA%20Final%20Report.pdf>
- Chapter I - Introduction. (n.d.). Retrieved January 12, 2018, from http://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/bitstream/10603/8799/8/08_chapter%201.pdf
- Chapter 2.2. Elementary Education. (n.d.). Retrieved January 12, 2018, from http://planningcommission.nic.in/plans/planrel/fiveyr/10th/volume2/v2_ch2_2.pdf
- Mehta, A. C. (2011). *Elementary education in India*. National University of Educational Planning and Administration. Retrieved January 11, 2018, from <http://dise.in/Downloads/Publications/Publications%202008-09/AR%202008-09/Introduction.pdf>
- Mukhopadhyay, R., Ramkumar, N., & Vasavi, A. R. (2009). *Management of elementary education: Structures and strategies*. National University of Educational Planning and Administration. Retrieved January 12, 2018, from <http://www.educationforallinindia.com/management-of-elementary-education-in-india.pdf>
- Shiva Kumar, A. K., & Rustagi, P. (2010). *Elementary education in India: Progress, setbacks and challenges*. Oxfam India Working Papers Series. Retrieved January 11, 2018, from <https://www.oxfamindia.org/sites/default/files/III.%20Elementary%20Education%20in%20India-Progress,%20Setbacks,%20and%20Challenges.pdf>